

Formation Of Competence In Using Information And Communication Media Of Future Primary Class Teachers

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Abstract: The modern era of society's development is characterized by the strong influence of communication technologies that permeate all spheres of human activity, ensure the spread of information flows in society, and shape the global information space. An integral and important part of these processes is the computerization of education. In this article, there are opinions about the forms of training future primary school teachers to form information competence and their pedagogical activity and competence in digitalization conditions. It is no secret that the use of information and communication tools has brought the educational process to a new level. Scientific studies on the use of information and communication technologies in all areas and stages of education and the formation of the competence of pedagogues emphasize the importance of the issue and recommend the use of modern technologies in this regard.

Key words: Primary education, information competence, model, software, digital education, technology, communicative competence.

Introduction.

In the socio-political, agricultural and ethno-cultural environment of the development of Uzbekistan, the system of primary education using information and communication technologies, national and social requirements for the development of professional communicative competence, are becoming an indispensable part of personal and professional life. Learning professional communicative competence using information and communication technologies provides a solid foundation for the acquisition of skills and knowledge.

Currently, a new education system is being formed in Uzbekistan, aimed at entering the global information and educational space. This process is accompanied by serious changes in the pedagogical theory and practice of the educational process, associated with adjustments to the content of educational technologies, which should correspond to modern technical capabilities and contribute to the harmonious entry of the child into the information society. Information and communication tools are not intended to be an adjunct to teaching, but rather to become an integral part of the holistic learning process, significantly increasing the effectiveness of learning.

"Planned outcomes of primary education" indicate that primary school teachers should form the competence in the use of information and communication technologies, that is, the ability of a person to solve educational, household, and professional problems using information and communication technologies. The competence in the use of information and communication tools is manifested in the activity of solving various problems involving computers, telecommunications, the Internet, etc. [1, 45-b].

The competence of an information and communication tool teacher is a set of knowledge, skills and experience in the use of communication tools in education [3, 257-b]. The competence in using information and communication tools consists of two components: general competence and professional competence. General information

and communication competence includes the following:

In the content and structure of the competence in the use of information and communication tools, it is possible to distinguish general pedagogical and subject components.

The general pedagogical component is the general directions of using information technologies in the educational and educational processes.

The subject component is the specific directions reflecting the characteristics of academic disciplines [1, 51-b].

Literature analysis and methodology.

A. Elizarov divides the teacher's qualification in using information and communication tools into three levels [3, 251-b]:

1. The invariant of knowledge, skills and experience necessary for each teacher and open to everyone in solving educational problems with the help of using information and communication tools of the main and universal purpose:

- mastering generally accepted tools for working in the personal information space on a computer (file operations and graphical interface);
- mastering the skills necessary to use the basic capabilities of office technology;
- using navigation technologies and searching for the necessary information on the Internet;
- using electronic mail and network communication technologies;
- an overview of multimedia and network educational resources.

2. Expanded - involves a deeper selection and development of the required information technologies that shape the professional activity of the teacher and prepare them for continuous inclusion in the real educational process through the use of information and communication tools in accordance with the requirements set for the educational content. At this level, the teacher develops technological skills for presenting his/her educational and methodological information, as well as skills for presenting an electronic pedagogical portfolio.

The advanced level involves processing text, graphic, audio, video information, deeper penetration into the field of computing technologies, mastering specialized technologies and resources developed in accordance with the requirements of the content, mastering technologies for presenting one's own information using a training, web interface (creating web pages and websites) and placing it on the Internet.

3. Specialized [3, 256-b].

It is important to distinguish between the teacher's information communication literacy and the competence in using information and communication tools. Information communication literacy is knowing what a personal computer is, what software products, their functions and capabilities are, the ability to "press the right buttons", and the existence of computer networks.

The competence in using information and communication tools is not only the use of various information tools, but also their effective application in pedagogical activities [4, 17-b].

Discussion.

The competence in the use of information and communication tools is understood by teachers as the confident possession of all the structural skills of information and

communication literacy to solve problems that arise in teaching and other activities, with an emphasis on the formation of generalized cognitive, ethical and technical skills [2, 74-b].

The content of the basic and advanced levels of the teacher's competence in the use of information and communication tools can be presented by two groups:

- the presence of ideas about the use of information and communication tools in the specific characteristics of pedagogical activity in accordance with educational tasks;

- the level of mastery of information processing methods with the use of information and communication tools in the process of organizing and implementing the pedagogical process [3, 254-b].

According to A. Elizarov, the basic level of competence in the use of information and communication tools includes the following:

- the presence of common ideas about the possibilities of using information and communication tools in pedagogical practice;

- the presence of ideas about electronic learning resources;

- the presence of ideas about the purpose and operation of the computer, input and output devices, local area networks and the possibilities of using them in the educational process;

- methods of organizing personal information space and the graphical interface of the operating system (methods of performing file operations, organization of the information environment as a file system, basic methods of input and output of information);

- possessing methods for preparing methodological materials and documents in accordance with the educational content and information technology tools (methods of entering text from the keyboard and formatting it; preparing materials containing graphic elements using established means of processing graphic elements; working with tabular data to create lists and tables using established methods of calculating the simplest data methods; graphic and diagram techniques; methods for creating presentations and demonstrations for use in pedagogical practice);

- mastering the basic services and methods of working on the Internet for use in educational activities (navigation and search for educational information on the Internet, methods of obtaining and storing it for subsequent use in pedagogical practice; methods of working with electronic mail; methods of working with network communication tools) [5, 144-b].

An analysis of existing methods for assessing the competence of teachers in the use of information and communication tools shows that existing methods for assessing information and communication competence are aimed at shaping the technological skills of teachers. The assessment of higher-level intellectual abilities that ensure full information and communication competence of teachers is almost not discussed today. For this reason, it is not possible to use the tools available today to measure teachers' competence in the use of information and communication technologies.

One of the results of the process of informatization of education should be the emergence of teachers' ability to use modern information and communication technologies to work with information. They should have the ability to search for,

organize, process, analyze and evaluate the necessary information, as well as process and disseminate information in accordance with their goals and the characteristics of the audience's perception.

Results.

In connection with the above, it was decided to develop new tools for assessing the competence in using information and communication tools, which will allow to check how a teacher thinks and works in the "digital" world. The assessment of the competence in using information and communication tools will be carried out according to the results of tests taken by teachers on a computer, and the general competence of teachers will be assessed based on the final result. Structural skills are not isolated and are assessed individually. The test presents several tasks to assess each of the structural skills, but in general, a high-quality (diagnostic) assessment is given for the test, reflecting the level of competence: the level is above the base, below the base, below the base.

Diagnostic assessment allows you to learn the knowledge and technical skills that go beyond the specific components of the ICT competency. The results of this type of test allow you to:

- provide a general assessment of the teacher's cognitive and technical competence;
- provide a detailed system of reporting on the accumulated scores, highlighting the teacher's specific strengths and weaknesses;
- link to existing or specially developed teaching materials;
- Based on the test results, it is possible to identify specific goals for teacher training [2, 78-b].

To identify an approximate list of the content of the teacher's competence in using information and communication tools [1, 47-b]. To know the list of the main electronic (digital) applications available on the subject: electronic textbooks, atlases, collections of digital educational resources on the Internet, etc.

Find, evaluate, select and display information from digital educational resources in accordance with the established learning objectives (for example, using electronic textbooks and other application materials on disks and on the Internet).

Be able to effectively transform and present information to solve educational problems, create your own educational material from available sources, summarize, compare, contrast, transform various information.

Conclusion.

It is necessary to effectively use the means of organizing student learning activities (test programs, electronic workbooks, systems for organizing student learning activities, etc.).

The new content of training for primary school teachers is aimed at shaping the thinking, independence, and educational activity of primary school teachers, taking into account the capabilities of students, using information technology tools and methods, developing logic, and assimilating and actively perceiving the laws of the logic of the information and communication world in students' thinking.

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